

A Note on 1-Edge Balance Index Set

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Abstract: Let G be a graph with vertex set V and edge set E , and $Z_2 = \{0, 1\}$. Let f be a labeling from E to Z_2 , so that the labels of the edges are 0 or 1. The edges labelled 1 are called 1-edges and edges labelled 0 are called 0-edges. The edge labeling f induces a vertex labeling $f^* : V \rightarrow Z_2$ defined by

$$f^*(v) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the number of 1-edges incident on } v \text{ is odd,} \\ 0 & \text{if the number of 1-edges incident on } v \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$

For $i \in Z_2$ let $e_f(i) = e(i) = |\{e \in E : f(e) = i\}|$ and $v_f(i) = v(i) = |\{v \in V : f^*(v) = i\}|$. A labeling f is said to be edge-friendly if $|e(0) - e(1)| \leq 1$. The 1-edge balance index set (OEBSI) of a graph G is defined by $\{|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| : \text{the edge labeling } f \text{ is edge-friendly}\}$. The main purpose of this paper is to completely determine the 1-edge balance index set of wheel and Mycielskian graph of a path.

Key Words: Mycielskian graph, edge labeling, edge-friendly, 1-edge balance index set, Smarandachely induced vertex labeling, Smarandachely edge-friendly graph.

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§1. Introduction

A graph labeling is an assignment of integers to the vertices or edges or both, subject to certain conditions. Varieties of graph labeling have been investigated by many authors [2], [3] [5] and they serve as useful models for broad range of applications.

Let G be a graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$ and $Z_2 = \{0, 1\}$. Let f be a labeling from $E(G)$ to Z_2 , so that the labels of the edges are 0 or 1. The edges labelled 1 are called 1-edges and edges labelled 0 are called 0-edges. The edge labeling f induces a vertex labeling $f^* : V(G) \rightarrow Z_2$, defined by

$$f^*(v) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the number of 1-edges incident on } v \text{ is odd,} \\ 0 & \text{if the number of 1-edges incident on } v \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$

For $i \in Z_2$, let $e_f(i) = e(i) = |\{e \in E(G) : f(e) = i\}|$ and $v_f(i) = v(i) = |\{v \in V(G) : f^*(v) = i\}|$. Generally, let $f : E(G) \rightarrow Z_p$ be a labeling from $E(G)$ to Z_p for an integer

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$p \geq 2$. A *Smarandachely induced vertex labeling* on G is defined by $f^v = (l_1, l_2, \dots, l_p)$ with $n_k(v) \equiv l_k \pmod{p}$, where $n_k(v)$ is the number of k -edges, i.e., edges labeled with an integer k incident on v . Let

$$e_k(G) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{e \in E(G)} n_k(v)$$

for an integer $1 \leq k \leq p$. Then a Smarandachely edge-friendly graph is defined as follows.

Definition 1.1 A graph G is said to be *Smarandachely edge-friendly* if $|e_k(G) - e_{k+1}(G)| \leq 1$ for integers $1 \leq k \leq p$. Particularly, if $p = 2$, such a Smarandachely edge-friendly graph is abbreviated to an *edge-friendly graph*.

Definition 1.2 The *1-edge balance index set* of a graph G , denoted by $OEBI(G)$, is defined as $\{|v_f(1) - v_f(0)| : f \text{ is edge-friendly}\}$.

For convenience, a vertex is called 0-vertex if its induced vertex label is 0 and 1-vertex, if its induced vertex label is 1.

In the mid 20th century there was a question regarding the construction of triangle-free k -chromatic graphs, where $k \leq 3$. In this search Mycielski [4] developed an interesting graph transformation known as the Mycielskian which is defined as follows:

Definition 1.3 For a graph $G = (V, E)$, the *Mycielskian* of G is the graph $\mu(G)$ with vertex set consisting of the disjoint union $V \cup V' \cup \{v_0\}$, where $V' = \{x' : x \in V\}$ and edge set $E \cup \{x'y : xy \in E\} \cup \{x'v_0 : x' \in V'\}$.

Figure 1 Mycielskian graph of the path P_n

Recently Chandrashekar Adiga et al. [1] have introduced and studied the 1-edge balance index set of several classes of graphs. In Section 2, we completely determine the 1-edge balance index set of the Mycielskian graph of path P_n . In Section 3, we establish that $OEBI(W_n) = \{0, 4, 8, \dots, n\}$ if $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, $OEBI(W_n) = \{2, 6, 10, \dots, n\}$ if $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ and $OEBI(W_n) = \{1, 2, 5, \dots, n\}$ if n is odd.

§2. The 1-Edge Balance Index Set of $\mu(P_n)$

In this section we consider the Mycielskian graph of the path P_n ($n \geq 2$), which consists of $2n+1$ vertices and $4n-3$ edges. To determine the $OEBI(\mu(P_n))$ we need the following theorem, whose proof is similar to the proof of the Theorem 1 in [6].

Theorem 2.1 *If the number of vertices in a graph G is even(odd) then the 1-edge balance index set contains only even(odd)numbers.*

Now we divide the problem of finding $OEBI(\mu(P_n))$ into two cases, viz,

$$n \equiv 0(\text{mod } 2) \quad \text{and} \quad n \equiv 1(\text{mod } 2),$$

Denoted by $\max\{OEBI(\mu(P_n))\}$ the largest number in the 1-edge balance index set of $\mu(P_n)$. Then we get the following result.

Theorem 2.2 *If $n \equiv 0(\text{mod } 2)$ i.e, $n = 2k(k \in N)$, then $OEBI(\mu(P_n)) = \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2n+1\}$.*

Proof Let f be an edge-friendly labeling on $\mu(P_n)$. Since the graph contains $2n+1 = 4k+1$ vertices, $4n-3 = 8k-3$ edges, we have two possibilities: i) $e(0) = 4k-1$, $e(1) = 4k-2$ ii) $e(0) = 4k-2$, $e(1) = 4k-1$. Now we consider the first case namely $e(0) = 4k-1$ and $e(1) = 4k-2$. Denote the vertices of $\mu(P_n)$ as in the Figure 1. Now we label the edges $u_{2q-1}v_{2q}$, $u_{2q+1}v_{2q}$ for $1 \leq q \leq k-1$, $u_q u_{q+1}$ for $1 \leq q \leq 2k-3$, $u_{2k-2}v_{2k-1}$, $u_{2k}v_{2k-1}$ and $u_{2k-1}u_{2k}$ by 1 and label the remaining edges by 0. Then it is easy to observe that $v(0) = 4k+1$ and there is no 1-vertex in the graph. Thus $|v(1) - v(0)| = 4k+1 = 2n+1 = \max\{OEBI(\mu(P_n))\}$.

Now we interchange the labels of the edges to get the remaining 1-edge balance index numbers. By interchanging the labels of edges $u_{2q}u_{2q+1}$ and $u_{2q}v_{2q+1}$ for $1 \leq q \leq k-2$, we get, $|v(0) - v(1)| = 4k+1-4q$. Further interchanging $u_{2k-1}u_{2k}$ and $u_{2k-1}v_{2k}$, we get $|v(0) - v(1)| = 5$.

In the next four steps we interchange two pairs of edges as follows to see that $1, 3, 7, 11 \in OEBI(\mu(P_n))$

$$\begin{aligned} &u_1v_2 \text{ and } v_1v_0, u_2v_3 \text{ and } v_2v_0. \\ &u_3v_2 \text{ and } v_3v_0, u_3v_4 \text{ and } v_4v_0. \\ &u_4v_5 \text{ and } v_5v_0, u_5v_4 \text{ and } v_6v_0. \\ &u_5v_6 \text{ and } v_7v_0, u_6v_7 \text{ and } v_8v_0. \end{aligned}$$

Now we interchange $u_{2\lfloor \frac{q-1}{2} \rfloor+7}$ $v_{2\lceil \frac{q-1}{2} \rceil+6}$ and v_{2q+7} v_0 , u_{2q+6} v_{2q+7} and v_{2q+8} v_0 for $1 \leq q \leq k-5$ to obtain $|v(0) - v(1)| = 4q+11$. Finally by interchanging the labels of the edges $u_{2\lfloor \frac{k-5}{2} \rfloor+7}$ $v_{2\lceil \frac{k-5}{2} \rceil+6}$ and u_{2k-2} u_{2k-1} we get $|v(0) - v(1)| = 4k-5$ and $u_{2\lfloor \frac{k-4}{2} \rfloor+7}$ $v_{2\lceil \frac{k-4}{2} \rceil+6}$ and u_{2k-1} v_0 we get $|v(0) - v(1)| = 4k-1$.

Proof of the second case follows similarly. Thus

$$OEBI(\mu(P_n)) = \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2n+1\}. \quad \square$$

Theorem 2.3 *If $n \equiv 1(\text{mod } 2)$ i.e, $n = 2k+1(k \in N)$, then $OEBI(\mu(P_n)) = \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2n+1\}$.*

Proof Let f be an edge-friendly labeling on $\mu(P_n)$. Since the graph contains $2n+1 = 4k+3$ vertices, $4n-3 = 8k+1$ edges, we have two possibilities: i) $e(0) = 4k+1$, $e(1) = 4k$ ii) $e(0) = 4k$, $e(1) = 4k+1$. Now we consider the first case namely $e(0) = 4k+1$ and $e(1) = 4k$. Denote the vertices of $\mu(P_n)$ as in the Figure 1. Now we label the edges $u_{2q-1}v_{2q}$, $u_{2q+1}v_{2q}$ for $1 \leq q \leq k$ and $u_q u_{q+1}$ for $1 \leq q \leq 2k$ by 1 and label the remaining edges by 0. Then it is easy to observe that $v(0) = 4k+3$ and there is no 1-vertex in the graph. Thus $|v(1) - v(0)| = 4k+3 = 2n+1 = \max\{OEBI(\mu(P_n))\}$.

Now we interchange the labels of the edges to get the remaining 1-edge balance index numbers. By interchanging the labels of edges $u_{2q}u_{2q+1}$ and $u_{2q}v_{2q+1}$ for $1 \leq q \leq k$ we get $|v(0) - v(1)| = 4k+3-4q$. Further interchanging $u_{2k}v_{2k+1}$ and $v_{2k+1}v_0$ we get $|v(0) - v(1)| = 1$.

In the next four steps we interchange two pairs of edges as follows to see that $5, 9, 13, 17 \in OEBI(\mu(P_n))$

$$\begin{aligned} &u_1v_2 \text{ and } v_1v_0, u_2v_3 \text{ and } v_2v_0. \\ &u_3v_2 \text{ and } v_3v_0, u_3v_4 \text{ and } v_4v_0. \\ &u_4v_5 \text{ and } v_5v_0, u_5v_4 \text{ and } v_6v_0. \\ &u_5v_6 \text{ and } v_7v_0, u_6v_7 \text{ and } v_8v_0. \end{aligned}$$

And finally by interchanging the labels of edges $u_{2\lfloor \frac{q-1}{2} \rfloor + 7} v_{2\lceil \frac{q-1}{2} \rceil + 6}$ and $v_{2q+7} v_0$, $u_{2q+6} v_{2q+7}$ and $v_{2q+8} v_0$ for $1 \leq q \leq k-4$, we Obtain $|v(0) - v(1)| = 4q+17$.

Proof of the second case follows similarly. Thus

$$OEBI(\mu(P_n)) = \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2n+1\}. \quad \square$$

§3. The 1-Edge Balance Index Set of Wheel

In this section we consider the wheel, denoted by W_n which consists of n vertices and $2n-2$ edges. To determine the $OEBI(W_n)$ we consider four cases, namely,

$$\begin{aligned} n &\equiv 0 \pmod{4}, & n &\equiv 1 \pmod{4}, \\ n &\equiv 2 \pmod{4}, & n &\equiv 3 \pmod{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.1 *If $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$ i.e, $n = 4k(k \in \mathbb{N})$, then $OEBI(W_n) = \{0, 4, 8, \dots, n\}$.*

Proof Let f be an edge-friendly labeling on W_n . Since the graph contains $n = 4k$ vertices, $2n-2 = 8k-2$ edges, we must have $e(0) = e(1) = 4k-1$. Denote the vertices on the rim of the wheel by $v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{4k-1}$ and denote the center by v_0 . Now we label the edges $v_q v_{q+1}$ for $1 \leq q \leq 4k-2$ and $v_{4k-1} v_1$ by 1 and label the remaining edges by 0. Then it is easy to observe that $v(0) = 4k$ and there is no 1-vertex in the graph. Thus $|v(1) - v(0)| = 4k = n = \max\{OEBI(W_n)\}$.

Now we interchange the labels of the edges to get the remaining 1-edge balance index numbers. By interchanging the labels of edges $v_{2q-1}v_{2q}$ and $v_{2q-1}v_0$, $v_{2q}v_{2q+1}$ and $v_{2q}v_0$ for $1 \leq q \leq k$ we get $|v(0) - v(1)| = 4k-4q$. Thus $0, 4, 8, \dots, n$ are elements of $OEBI(W_n)$.

Let $a_i = \text{card}\{v \in V \mid \text{number of 1-edges incident on } v \text{ is equal to } i\}$, $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 4k - 1$. Then we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^{4k-1} ia_i = a_1 + 2a_2 + 3a_3 + \dots + (4k - 1)a_{4k-1} = 8k - 2$$

implies that $a_1 + 3a_3 + 5a_5 + \dots + (4k - 1)a_{4k-1}$ is even, which is possible if and only if, $a_1 + a_3 + a_5 + \dots + a_{4k-1}$ is even, that is, the number of 1-vertices is even and hence the number of 0-vertices is also even. Therefore, the numbers $2, 6, 10, \dots, n - 2$ are not elements of $OEBI(W_n)$. \square

Theorem 3.2 *If $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ i.e., $n = 4k + 1 (k \in N)$, then $OEBI(W_n) = \{1, 3, 5, \dots, n\}$.*

Proof Let f be an edge-friendly labeling on W_n . Since the graph contains $n = 4k + 1$ vertices, $2n - 2 = 8k$ edges, we must have $e(0) = e(1) = 4k$. Denote the vertices on the rim of the wheel by $v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{4k}$ and denote the center by v_0 . Now we label the edges $v_q v_{q+1}$ for $1 \leq q \leq 4k - 1$ and $v_{4k} v_1$ by 1 and label the remaining edges by 0. Then it is easy to observe that $v(0) = 4k + 1$ and there is no 1-vertex in the graph. Thus $|v(1) - v(0)| = 4k + 1 = n = \max\{OEBI(W_n)\}$.

Now we interchange the labels of the edges to get the remaining 1-edge balance index numbers. By interchanging the labels of edges $v_{2q-1} v_{2q}$ and $v_{2q-1} v_0$, $v_{2q} v_{2q+1}$ and $v_{2q} v_0$ for $1 \leq q \leq 2k - 1$, we get $|v(0) - v(1)| = |4k + 1 - 4q|$ and by interchanging the labels of edges $v_{4k-1} v_{4k}$ and $v_{4k-1} v_0$, $v_{4k} v_1$ and $v_{4k} v_0$, we get $|v(0) - v(1)| = 4k - 1$. Thus

$$OEBI(W_n) = \{1, 3, 5, \dots, n\}. \quad \square$$

Similarly one can prove the following results.

Theorem 3.3 *If $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ i.e., $n = 4k + 2 (k \in N)$, then $OEBI(W_n) = \{2, 6, 10, \dots, n\}$.*

Theorem 3.4 *If $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ i.e., $n = 4k + 3 (k \in N)$, then $OEBI(W_n) = \{1, 3, 5, \dots, n\}$.*

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